
“A Cross Sectional Study to Assess the Behavioral Problems of Children among Working and Non Working Mothers in Rural Areas of Chittoor, Ap”

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ABSTRACT

Background of the Study: Children are the wealth of tomorrow. Behavioral problems in the childhood period is the strongest predictor of more serious problems in later life. Screening is necessary to detect behavioral problems among children.

Aim: The present study was conducted to assess the behavioral problems among 6-10 years children of working and non-working mothers in rural areas of chittoor ,AP.

Methodology: A cross sectional comparative research design was adopted to conduct the research study.Non probability convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data. Tools used for the present study were three point Likert scale to assess behavioral problems among children under the age of 6-10 years. In this study,total 60 samples were taken,30 working and 30 non-working mothers of children under age of 6-10 years of rural areas of Chittoor, Andhra Pradesh to assess the behavioural problems were included in this study.

Results:A study reveals that 10% of working mothers and 20% of non-working mothers reported normal behavior in their children and 30% of working mothers and 15% of non working mothers reported mild behavior and 15% of working mothers and 10% of non-working mothers reported moderate behavior in their children.

Conclusion:The study concluded that the children of 6-10 years of working and nonworking mothers has non significant behavioural problems as evidenced by purposive sampling techniques. The study was contented in the rural areas of chittoor Andhra Pradesh.Tools used for the present study were three point Likert scale to asses the common behavioral problem among the children of working and non working mother, non probability convenient sampling technique were used to collect the data .There is significant difference in the level of behavioral problems of children among working and non working mother.

INTRODUCTION

Children are the inheritance from god. They are like the potters hand , handled with love and care. Every child have tender loving care and sense of security from parents. The mothers are more responsible for the integrated development of the child. Children are the nations most important assets, and are most potential unit of our future Human Resources in a developing country like India.³ Mother plays a major role in the development of personal characteristics, social behaviour, emotional adjustment and motivation of the child . However, the present scenario is such that it is not feasible to make a living with just one person's earnings. Hence, women set out to support their family. This in turn leads to lack of time in working women/mother for personal needs and also for family needs.⁶

Childhood is the period of dependency, and they learn to adjust in the environment. But there in any complexity around them they cannot adjust with that circumstances then they become unable to balance I'm socially acceptable way and behaviour problems develop with them.²

OBJECTIVES

Behavioral Problems Among Children of working mothers and non-working mothers of Selected Rural Area, Chittoor-AP

1. To assess the level of behavioral problems among children of working mothers.
2. To assess the level of behavioral problems among children of non-working mothers.
3. To compare the behavioral problems among children of working mothers and non-working mothers.

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4. To find out the association between behavioral problems among children of working and non-working mothers with their selected demographic variables.

METHODOLOGY

The present study has been aimed to assess the knowledge of behavioural problem in children(6-10year) among working and non working mother at Murukambattu ,chittoor .Population is the entire aggregation of cases that meet a designated set if criteria. In this present study population consist of children under the age of 6-10 years of working and non-working mother at the rural area of Chittoor-AP.

Criteria For Sample Selection

Inclusive criteria

- Children of working mother residing in Murukambattu,chittoor.
- Mother who are doing work from home, part time, office, worker, small scale business at home.
- Mother who knows English.
- Mothers who are all housewives

Exclusive Criteria

- >Non-working mothers who are not willing to participate in the study.
- >Working mothers who are not available at the time of data collection.
- >Non -working mothers who are not available at the time of data collect
- >Mother who can't read Telugu and English.

Description of the study:

Section-A

>It includes demographic variables such as eye education of the children, family income, education of father, education of mother, occupation of mother, occupation of father, and source of information.

Section- B

>It consist of multiple choice question to assess behavioural problems among the children at Murukambattu ,chittoor.

Data collection procedure

Our study was conducted on 01/09/2025 to 07/09/2025 It was decided to take 60 samples from rural area of, Chittoor -AP. First we conducted 30 non-working mothers next 30 samples we conducted for working mothers.It was decided to collect minimum 10 samples per day from 01/09/2025 to 07/09/2025 at 3pm to 6pm. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used for this study.. Participant sit comfortably and introduced ourself to each participant and explained the purpose of study and took a written consent from them.The investigator administered questioner to the participants and asked them to select the correct answer and put a tick mark.The data collection took 15-20minutes for completions from each participants .The participants were thanked for there willingness and co-operation the same procedure was followed for all 60 samples. The investigator thanks the respondent for their willingness and cooperation.The samples are selected based on inclusive criteria.

Data analysis

The data was collected and analyzed by using descriptive study.

Score interpretation:

An interview schedule was used to assess the behavioural problems of children of working and non working mothers. It contains 40 questions according to likert scale. The working and non working mothers are interviewed using descriptive questionnaire. Sometime occurrence of symptoms was given score of 'one' and for 'absence of symptoms' was given score of 'zero'. The total score is 40.

The score was interpreted as follows:

- *0 - occurs no time
- *1 - sometime occurs
- *2.5 - occurs always

Data analysis

This chapter deals with the statistical analysis and interpretation of the data. The data were analyzed based on the objectives of the study. The data was collected among 30 working women and 30 non working women in selected rural areas at ,Chittoor -AP. Presentation of the data:The data were organized and presented under following data SECTION-I:

Frequency and Percentage distribution of socio demographic variables among women . SECTION - II:

Frequency and Percentage distribution of knowledge regarding behavioral problems in children under 6-10 among working

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and non working mothers.

SECTION - III:

Mean and standard deviation level of knowledge regarding behavioral problems in children of 6-10 among working and non working mothers.

SECTION - IV:

Association between the level of knowledge regarding behavioral problems in children of 6-10 among working and non working mothers. and their socio demographic variables.

DISCUSSION

1. To assess the level of behavioral problems among children of working mothers. The study reveals that 10% of working mothers reported normal behavior in their children and 30% of working mothers reported mild behavior and 15% of working mothers reported moderate behavior in their children.

Prakasam A, Tarabada E, et.al (2023) :Behavioral problems among children of working and non working mothers in a selected area. A large number of children suffer from behavioral problems at one time the another during their development. The present study aimed to identify the level of behavioral problems among 1 children of working mothers and non-working mothers. The children years extending from approximately 6-10 years of age, the causes for all behavioral problems in children are parents' negligence, poor supervision, poor attention, and maladjustment e.g., too strict parents, rejection, insecurity aggression. A descriptive research design was adopted using a non probability purposive sampling technique to collect the 60 samples by administering Five-point Likert Scale on behavioral problems. Data were analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics such as standard deviation, and chi square-test. The finding shows that 8.0%(4) of working mothers had their children with severe behavioral problems and 34.0% (17) children with moderate behavioral problems. 32.0% (16) non-working mothers had their children with mild behavioral problems and 8.0%(4) children with moderate behavioral problems. Also found that there is no significant association between the behavioral problems of children with their selected demographic variables. The findings of the study concluded that the majority of children of working mothers had behavioral problems as compared to non-working mothers. purposive sampling techniques. The study was conducted in the pediatric outpatient department with Achenbach's modified child behaviour checklist was used to assess the common behavioral problems among working mothers of children. inferential and descriptive statistics were used for data analysis.

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted with the purpose of assessing the Behavioral problems of children among working and non-working mothers in urban area of Murukambattu, Chittoor. On the basis of the results it can be concluded that there was a significant difference in the occurrence of behavioral problems in children among working and non-working mothers. Majority of the children, 18(60%) among working mothers were having Borderline behaviour whereas among non-working mothers majority of children, 17(56.67%) were having normal Behavior. Furthermore it explores a higher level of hyperactivity, habit and social adjustment problems in children among working mothers. The research findings also reported a greater level of anxiety and conduct problems among children of non-working mothers. This study confirms that there was a significant association between Behavioral problems of children and their selected demographic variables such as type of family, birth order and gender of the child at 0.05 level of significance.

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